

A Study on Customer Satisfaction of Online Consumer Goods With Special -Reference to Chennai

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Abstract

Web business offers different electronic elevating opportunities to organizations around the world and closes by high fast improvement of online shopping; it has awed various retailers to pitch things and organizations through an online channel to expand their market. Online shopping or publicizing is the use of development (i.e., PC, web) for better advancing execution. Furthermore, retailers are mixing strategies to deal with the interest of online clients; they are involved in inspecting customer in the field of web shopping, to see the purchaser tempers towards electronic shopping and expressly thinking about the components affecting buyers to shop on the web. This research found that the overwhelming components which influence consumer perceptions towards online purchasing, such as, convenience in searching products, the relevance of product recommendations and security/privacy. Consumer conduct is said to be a connected control as a few choices are essentially influenced by their conduct or anticipated activities. The two points of view that look for utilization of its information are smaller scale and societal perspectives. This article also highlights the role of demographic factors like Age, Gender, Income, Marital status affecting the Consumer Behaviour towards online marketing.

Keywords: Consumer behaviour, online marketing, marketing strategies, E- business

Introduction

Internet is changing the manner in which customers shop and purchase merchandise and ventures, and has quickly developed into a worldwide wonder. Numerous organizations have begun utilizing the Internet with the point of cutting advertising costs, consequently reducing cost of their items and administrations so as to remain ahead in profoundly focused markets. Organizations likewise utilize the Internet to pass on conveys and scatter data, to move the item, to take criticism and furthermore to direct fulfilment reviews with clients. Clients utilize the web not exclusively to purchase the item on the web, yet additionally to analyze costs, item includes and after deal benefit offices and so on., towards on line promoting. Numerous specialists are hopeful about the possibility of online business. Notwithstanding the huge capability of the E-business showcase, the Internet gives a one of a kind chance to organizations to all the more effectively achieve existing and potential clients. Albeit the greater part of the income of online exchanges originates from business to business, the experts of business-to-shopper ought not lose certainty. It has been

over 10 years since E-business-to-shopper originally developed. Researchers and professionals of electronic trade continually endeavour to pick up an enhanced knowledge into purchaser conduct in the internet. Alongside the advancement of E-retailing, the examination keeps on clarifying E consumers’ conduct from alternate points of view. A large number of the examinations have presented new developing components or suspicions which depend on the conventional models of customer conduct, and after that look at their legitimacy in the Internet context.

Literature Review

Mohan Kumar and Shiva Shanthi (2016) This research found that the five overwhelming variables which impact consumer perceptions towards online purchasing, they are perceived usefulness factor, information, ease of use; perceived enjoyment and security/privacy. Consumer behaviour is said to be an applied discipline as some decisions are significantly affected by their behaviour or expected actions. The two perspectives that seek application of its knowledge are micro and societal perspectives. This article also highlights on the role of demographic factors like Age, Gender, Income, Marital status affecting on the Consumer Behaviour towards online marketing. **Vijay, Sai. T. & Balaji, M. S. (May 2009)**, revealed that Consumers, everywhere throughout the world, are progressively moving from the swarmed stores to the a single tick web based shopping position. Be that as it may, despite the comfort offered, web based shopping is a long way from being the most favoured type of shopping in India. An overview among 150 web clients, including the two clients and non-clients of web based shopping, was done to comprehend why some buy on the web while others don’t. The outcomes recommended that comfort and sparing of time drive Indian buyers to shop on the web; while security and protection concerns prevent them from doing as such. **Kim and Park (2005)** study suggests that their positive attitudes as well as willingness to search for pre-purchase information leads to a strong likelihood that they will purchase on the web. Online shoppers, are required to have computer skills in order to use the Internet for shopping. Hence, those who are not comfortable with using the computer, will likely do their shopping at the customary store, modern shop, or discount store. **Efthymios Constantinides (2004)** Web encounter must be viewed as a dynamic and advancing subject instead of a static one; advancements in the virtual commercial centre, changing client techno graphics and mechanical development will give e-advertisers new apparatuses and strategies for upgrading their clients’ online experience. In that regard this study depicts the current picture of the research done so far, a great beginning stage for further research toward building up a far reaching hypothesis on the web based purchasing behaviour. **Smith and Rupp (2003)** analyzed and distinguish the variables in their work that influences the conduct of purchasers. These issues have been identified concerning the advertising exertion, socio social influence, passionate factor, the mental elements and security factors, to the experience, the buy and post - buy choices. They likewise demonstrate that buyers are influenced by different mental variables, for example, observation, inspiration, identity, frames of mind and feelings.

Objectives of the Study

1. To explore the buyer conduct towards internet promoting.
2. To consider the factors affecting towards web based marketing.

Research Methodology

Data for this study was collected by means of a survey conducted in Chennai. The sample size was 100. The Questionnaire was used mainly to test the model proposed for attitude towards web shopping. The types of research were both exploratory as well as descriptive have been employed.

Research Design

This study has been fused descriptive research design.

Sample Design

The sample size used for the study is 100. Responses Collected from 100 respondents. The sampling population for this research was the people of Chennai as it was particularly concentrated on this geographical region. Convenience sampling technique has been used.

Data Sources

- Primary data: Data collected through structured questionnaire from the respondents.
- Secondary data includes the information obtained from the existing research reports, surveys, journals or magazines regarding consumer approach towards online shopping.

Data Analysis

The study has been used descriptive data analysis for the better outcome.

Limitations of the Study

1. The study examine only on consumer behaviour towards web marketing, geographical region restricted to Chennai only.
2. The data gathered from the respondents will most likely be unable to sum up because of the little example estimate.

Analysis and Interpretation

A combination of discussions, interview and questionnaire method is used to collect data from the respondents. Under sample design, random sampling method has been used to collect data from the respondents. A sample size of 100 respondents is taken for the collection of the data.

The following tables provides details about the respondents:

Classification of respondents on the basis of gender

Male	46 (46%)
Female	54 (54%)

The table results shows that 46 % of male and 54 % of female respondents participated in the online shopping survey. The number of female respondents is slightly higher than male respondents.

Classification of respondents on the basis of Age

15-25 years	10 (10%)
26-35	45 (45%)
36 -45	27 (27%)
Above 46 years	18 (18%)

The table indicated that 45 % of the respondents in the survey come under the category of 25-35 years age, 27 % participants come under the category of 35-45 years age group, while 18% come under the category of above 45 years of age.

Classification of respondents on the basis of Income

15000 – 25000	21 (21%)
25001-35000	42 (42%)
35001-45000	26 (26%)
Above45001	11 (11%)

The table revealed that the despondent with income between Rs. 25000 – 35000 are more attracted towards online shopping.

Classification of respondents on the basis of Education Level

Under Graduate	12 (12%)
Graduates	18 (18%)
Post Graduates	33 (33%)
Professionals	37 (37%)

The table shows that 37 professionally qualified, 33 post graduates, 18 graduates and rest 12 under graduates are having online shopping frequently.

Classification of respondents on the basis of Purpose of using internet (%)

Entertainment	30 (30%)
Easy shopping	35 (35%)
Gathering Information	20 (20%)
Entertainment	15 (15%)

The tale indicated that the results about 35 respondents are of the view that they have enjoyed with online shopping. 20 respondent replied that the purpose of using internet is together information, about 15 said that online shopping is easy and convenient as well.

Classification of respondents on the basis of Frequency of use of Internet

1-2 Hrs	20 (20%)
2-4 Hrs	24 (24%)
4-6 Hrs	29 (29%)
More than 6 Hrs	27 (27%)

The Table shows that frequency of using internet for this purpose is maximum in between 4-6 hours followed by more than 6 hours. But according to the results about 27 respondents are of the view that they have enjoyed with online shopping. 24 respondent replied that the purpose of using internet is together information, about 29 said that online shopping is easy and convenient as well.

Findings

The result of the study found that to the liable to be pulled in towards the limited time plans offered by the online retailers and in this way gender orientation has a significant affect on every now and again of on-line shopping. Rising Working women idea has additionally improved it. Pay as one of the factors of socioeconomics factor has a significant affect on effect Frequency of online buy of customers.

Conclusion

The study was accomplished to find out the impact of demographic factors on online. Online shopping is getting more popular in India as well as in rest of the world. As indicated by the overview, web based shopping is getting fame in the age, for example, post graduate understudies and experts. Students for the most part want to purchase products from its unique source and they for the most part lean toward web based shopping. At the point when a shopper to make buys online to purchase something, the person is influenced by grouped variables. Purchase online can be of extraordinary benefit to the purchaser as far as comfort, sparing time and cash. Middle income groups and educated people are purchasing more via websites. individuals have faltering in doing web based shopping because of security concerns. Some of the time, individuals are impervious to change on account of mechanical intricacy in making web based purchasing. Since India is a developing nation, it is as yet not set up for it. India is eager to develop to be a most critical player in this market. Furthermore, on-line shopping is an ongoing marvel in the field of E-Business and is definitely going to be the eventual fate of shopping in the world.

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